

Values Education: A Case Study of a Differently Abled School

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ABSTRACT : The paper presents some innovations in values education as carried out by Duttadariaton Swami Vivekananda Manan Kalyan Kendra, Bhabanandapur, Kalna, which is one of the developing and progressive schools for disable children. The curriculum of this special school emphasises on value-based education. This school is following three important objectives of education, namely knowledge, values and living skills. All the teachers of this school are following Functional Assessment Checklist for Programming as evaluation scale. Here the new strategies adopted for value transition includes: school-family interactions for excellence, which emphasises inter-family and intra-family interactions, inter-family competitions, and role of family in value improvement. The institution provides opportunities for global revelation to students. The school believes that "Every child is potentially the light of the world and at the same time the cause of its darkness". Every endeavour is consequently made to make every child good and smart; good at heart with high moral values, wisdom in thought and action, and smart in appearance, manners, etiquette and confidence. The paper further highlights the four decisive elements of complete education adapted by this school viz. (i) universal values, (ii) global understanding, (iii) excellence in all things, and (iv) service to humanity. The author also provides a detailed account of several innovations such as enrichment classes, teacher guardian, home visit scheme, quality control circles, model class presentations, creative music, and remediation in teaching.

Keywords : Values Education, Differently abled school, Universal Values, Enrichment Classes

Introduction

Differently abled schools are those schools where proper education is given to the children who are disabled in physical or behavioural term.

These types of special schools provide individualized education, addressing specific needs. Here the student-teacher ratio is very low. Here Education is as deep as the life itself and as broad as the world of our experiences. It

touches life at every point. It directs our thoughts, feelings and activity at every moment. Like other formal schools this differently able school considers a major vehicle in nurturing of values. Values and education are closely related; in fact they are the two sides of the same coin. The entire educational system and the educative process are manifestation, revelation and realisation of values considered worthwhile by individual and society from time to time. In formal schools values consideration should influence the entire educational process namely aims, curriculum, teaching methods institutional climate and interhuman relation. The differently abled school also provides these types of progression for nurturing values between the students. Here the author explores the exertion of Duttadariaton Swami Vivekananda Manan Kalyan Kendra, which is a differently abled school.

The School

The Duttadariaton Swami Vivekananda Manan Kalyan Kendra (SWVMKK), Kalna, Burdwan, was established in 1996 and started its working from 1997 by a visionary social worker Madan Mohan Ghosh. After a long ups and down the school got recognized from the Government of West Bengal in 2003 and was issued certificate persist with disability, sponsored by Bikash Bhavana in 2006. At present SWVMKK have 44 students, 8 teachers and 5 non teaching staffs. Here the student-teacher ratio is 6:1. It has distinguished itself as one of the fastest developing and most progressive school for differently abled children. This institution is dedicated to help the students with learning disabilities between the ages 5 to 18 years to develop the skills, knowledge, understanding and attitude necessary for them

to lead about fulfilling and producing lives and also making a successful individuals and active contributors in society. The children of this school begin their learning with their own body. According to the school, children first need to understand themselves, their bodies and then regulate themselves in order to learn. This is the sensory motor development. This sensory motor foundation actually builds the social, emotional, cognitive and language development.

Academics of the School

There are six units in this school - i) Pre-Primary, ii) Primary-1, iii) Primary-2, iv) Secondary, v) Pre-Vocational-I and vi) Pre-Vocational-II. After admitting the students the school observes them at about 15 days or so. In the mean time every parents have to fill up a Case History form about their children. After that the school organizes a medical check up for every student in Burdwan Medical College. Getting the testing reports the school selects the proper classes for every child. The classroom classification in operation is shown below-

Levels	Chronological Ages	Mental Ages
Pre-Primary Level (A)	3 – 6 Years	Up To 5 Years
Primary Level I	Over 6 Years	Around 4½ Years
Primary Level II	7 – 10 Years	5 – 7 Years
Secondary Level	10 – 13 Years	7 – 9 Years
Pre-Vocational Level	14 – 18 Years	8 + Years

The primary aim of the educators of this school is to develop the activities of the students for daily livings wherein inappropriate behaviour modification becomes simple. Functional

Assessment Checklist for Programming is used for giving promotion of students in this school. Each of the seven checklists is addressed to different levels of the child's functioning, namely, Pre-primary, Primary-I, Primary-II, Secondary, Pre-Vocational-I, and Pre-Vocational-II. At each level, students are selected carefully and the checklists are written objectively. The checklists cover a broad domain of skills, like personal, social, academic, occupational and recreational. When a child achieves 80% success at a given level, promotion to the next higher level is considered. Each item on the checklist is rated along a descriptive scale namely, Yes (+) means the child performs the item with no help, occasionally cueing (OC), verbal prompting (VP), physical prompting (PP), No (-) means one has to support the child completely in the performance of tasks. Teaching goals and objectives set are evaluated once in three months and the overall progress is evaluated at the end of each quarter. The checklist provides the periodic evaluation.

Inherent Values Ingrained in the School

At the individual level, nurturing values in school students needs to be seen as an investment in building the foundation for lifelong learning and promoting human excellence. The capacity to listen, cooperation, and team work, positive attitude towards study, work and life are the hallmarks of a good student or a person. So values, in fact, promote both academic as well as human excellence. In this sense education for values humanizes education. At the societal level, education for values aims at promoting social cohesion and national integration for transforming societies, nations and creating a better world. It can contribute to create the aspiration for transformation of the culture of

war, violence and greed into a culture of peace; where people learn and understand more about each other's uniqueness, human rights and fundamental freedom; where people learn to care and share to live together in a just, peaceful and empathetic society both in their urgent contexts and in the world at large. This institution is embedding warmly to fostering those values between students.

Universal Values

In its Preamble itself, Indian Constitution lays down four universal values: Justice, Liberty, Equality and Fraternity. The Justice to be truly meaningful needs sharing of power, compassion towards under-privileged and empathy towards the disadvantage. The institution ensures that every child should get the same care as they have needed. The students grasp the values for the integration of their life. Liberty of thought and action is a fundamental value embedded in our Constitution. Here the teachers stress on the creativity and experiments of new ideas that can advance social progress for the students. Respecting the rights of others to liberty of thought and action are the hall marks of a civilized society. Here the teacher use the strategies of child centric education by which the students get the opportunity to express their creative thoughts. Equality is another value enshrined in the Constitution. Freedom and justice remain mere words if the equality is not ensured. The teachers in this school do not offer any special care for any individual according to any caste, creed and socio economic status. The need and the care are the main devotions of the teachers towards their students. So here the students inculcate the fragments of equality. Fraternity is at the heart of school. Social

solidarity is a vital part of this society that has placed for the aspirations of all members of society. Ideally, the teachers of this institution endeavour to create a bonding between the school and their homes. Parents and teachers venture hand in hand to create an environment of encouragement, love and care so that every student grows up to become an ideal member of the society.

Global Understanding

Globalization means all peoples' impact on each others throughout the world. For example, the direct and indirect effects of pollution affect our life very much in whole world. Education plays a crucial role in helping children and young people to recognise their contribution and responsibilities as citizens of this global community and equipping them with the skills to make informed decisions and take responsible actions. The teachers of this institution are including the global dimension in their teaching that can be made links between local and global issues. It means also that students have given the opportunities to critically examine their own values and attitudes which appreciate the similarities between peoples and value diversity everywhere. They understand the global context in their local lives and develop skills that will enable them to combat the present ongoing injustices, prejudices and discriminations. Such knowledge, skills and understanding enables the students to play an active role in the global community.

Social Values

Inculcation of social values helps students to learn to appreciate, demonstrate sensitively and skills in fulfilling their responsibilities as citizens

towards shaping of a better society. Related attitudes and Skills : Awareness and respect for one's own and others rights and responsibilities, secularism, multiculturalism, sustainable development, ability to work with others in a cooperative way help them to make themselves as a good citizen. The heartiest involvement of the students in the school helps them to believe as a member of this family, neighbourhood, village, town, city, community, nation and global society. All the students are in full of neighbourhood feelings in them and whenever is needed, in their stipulated mind and feelings, they stands beside each others.

Excellence in All Things

This institution use different types of strategies to enable students to acquire positive attitudes and desirable habits for keeping themselves fit and healthy. Relating attitudes and Skills, they learn about cleanliness, healthy eating or food habits, fitness regime, Rest or relaxation, avoiding indulgence etc. Here Mid Day Meal programme is a crucial preserve for children's' health, particularly for children who are denied access to adequate nutrition and health care in their homes, which is the fundamental concern for human security. When they take food altogether they learn about teamwork, cooperation, self dependency etc.

Service to Humanity

The institution assembles an accurate circumstance to enable students presuming responsibility for their work and duty in the day-to-day learning and develop positive attitude and skills to work productively. If students assume responsibility of their action/behaviour in their own then they become willing to be accountable

to their actions and experience the consequences, good or bad, are not likely to take work casually or develop the tendency to blame others. Fostering values of responsibilities thus helps to lessen the extrinsic control and nurtures students' intrinsic motivation and self-confidence to meet and overcome challenges. Taking up the responsibilities for one's work helps in achieving one's goals, developing work skills, providing sense of accomplishment and faith in self and so on. Another important aspect here they inculcate is to enjoy one's work rather than taking it as a burden or pain. It is only the joy and happiness out of work which can sustain efforts towards completing the task.

Core Values

Here the books that students read, the school activities that students participate, the methods of teaching that are being used by teachers, the role of supervisor teachers and pupils are expected to play in the continuance of the rules and regulations of school, the manner in which particular events are celebrated and are chosen to exemplify their significance, the methods of evaluation, promotion, the way teachers are treated, the amount of freedom they enjoy, the kind of people serving on the school and the way administrative staff functions is monitored etc., reflect and symbolize values. The school atmosphere is surcharged with positive values to imbibe and internalize. Here all teachers are properly oriented to create such environment for children where those values become vibrant. Their preserve their role is to put the child on the right path not by imposing but by watching, suggesting, helping. Each unit of study in the textbook for different subjects is related to value concerns through exercises, examples,

question and discussion etc. as far as possible. Here teacher-student interactions provide a great treaty of openness.

Fostering Values in New Innovations

Here the students come from different families which are belonging to different types of socio-economic conditions. But the school maintains intra-family and inter-family bonding between them. They have done many works with mutual understanding and cooperation for the school. The old guardians give advice for the new guardians to take vital decision about their children. They participate in different programmes namely Annual Sports, Saraswati Puja, and Excursion etc., organized by the school. The relationship between teacher and guardians are so friendly that the teachers go visiting their students at their home if it is needed. Collecting information from the parents about the improvement of the students the teachers organize remedial classes. In these special classes they use music, drawing, playing, singing etc., as teaching strategies like a healing. Here the students learn how every difficulty can be succeeded and how they can conquer any types of problems in their lives.

Comparing Student-Teacher Relationship with other Formal Schools

In this century, learners are assumed to be collaborative, adaptive, informative, media and technology savvy, communicators, immediate and instant, require instant gratification, creators and adaptor and thus the society expects the teacher to be creative, constructive and technologically trained to adapt these means in the classroom teaching situations. Teachers cleave to a very elevated and esteemed position

as parents trust them more than anyone in the society as they consider teachers as the ultimate instruments of change. They also believe that the qualities like tolerance, acceptance, a wider view, global awareness, reflection and equal justice rests within the teachers to shape their child in all possible ways to face this competitive world of today. When child first time steps in school's desks, he tries to make relationship with people around him especially the teachers. If teacher start to understand his students there will be a good relationship, because when students have problems on school they can speak freely with their teachers and they can find solution together that is good for everyone. If that relationship and communication student-teacher is good, student will have more respect to the teacher and he will pay more attention on his classes. But now days the relationship become hectic position in our society. The reliability between students and teacher not so fine now a days in formal school.

But here the relationship between student-teacher is too much comfortable and humble. According to the Teacher in Charge of this school, a teacher basically has three roles, the first is the role in the class room - having to do with classroom management, the second is the role towards the students - it has to do with the personal interaction between the teacher and the learner, and the third is the role towards him or herself - the commitment of the teacher to continue in own personal development, to be the best he or she can be. Fortunately, all those above said three roles are well followed by all the teachers now in this institution. Students are thinking their teachers as *Gurus* like before. They maintain their duties beyond school time.

The children of this school are dependable indeed on their teachers than their parents.

Conclusion

It is always being difficult to run a school brimful with differently abled children. In the present days a formal school is running very extensively where all of the students cannot be handled properly by many teachers, discipline cannot be maintained properly, evaluation is also not able to judge a student flawlessly, the school like, Duttadariaton Swami Vivekananda Manan Kalyan Kendra, is really a path breaker in this milieu. It is really be observable by others that how well a school can be run with the immense dedication of all the teachers and obviously with the appreciative assistance of non teaching personnel there. In this quarrelsome world, the values of togetherness, the values for equality, and the values of humanity are clearly seen in this type of school. The students are so close to their teachers that sometimes some of the major decisions of them are being taken by the school teachers only and those are done very copiously with the prior help of their parents. The simplicity in their eyes just mesmerizes us. When many of us are now chatting about the relegate of humanity, values, compassion, empathy and ideals in schools, colleges and universities level, especially for the students and sometimes with some of the haughty teachers also, this school or this types of schools are showing the opposite flamboyant path, where the inherent values are not only making but also maintaining and bearing.

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